

Efficient water splitting via a flexible solar-powered Hybrid thermochemical-Sulphur dioxide depolarized Electrolysis Cycle

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D4.1 Solar-driven H₂ production concept - Public

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WP4 - Centrifugal solar particle receiver and particle storage

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Preface

HySelect will demonstrate the production of hydrogen (H₂) by splitting water via concentrated solar technologies (CST) with an attractive efficiency and cost, through the Hybrid Sulphur cycle (HyS). The HyS consists of two central steps: the high temperature -yet below-900 °C -decomposition of Sulphuric acid forming Sulphur dioxide (SO₂) and the subsequent low temperature (50-80 °C) SO₂ depolarized electrolysis (SDE) of water to produce H₂. HySelect will introduce, develop and operate under real conditions a complete H₂ production chain focusing on two innovative, full scale plant prototype core devices for both steps of the HyS cycle: an allothermally heated, spatially decoupled from a centrifugal particle solar receiver, Sulphuric acid decomposition-Sulphur trioxide splitting (SAD-STs) reactor and a Sulphur dioxide depolarized electrolyzer (SDE) without expensive Platinum Group Metals (PGMs). Furthermore, a heat recovery system will be integrated to exploit the temperature difference within the cycle and boost the overall process efficiency. In the course of the work, non-critical materials and catalysts will be developed, qualified and integrated into the plant scale prototype units for both the acid splitting reactor and the SDE unit. Experimental work will be accompanied by component modelling and overall process simulation and culminate with a demonstration of the complete process integrating its key units of a 750 kW_{th} centrifugal particle receiver, a hot particles storage system, a 250 kW_{th} SAD-STs and a 100 kW_e SDE into a pilot plant. Testing for a period of at least 6 months in a large-scale solar tower, driven with smart operation and control strategies, will establish the HySelect targeted efficiency and costs. Finally, an overall process evaluation will be carried out in order to assess the technical and economic prospects of the HySelect technology, directly linked to the know-how and developments of the Sulphuric acid and water electrolyzers industries.

DLR	German Aerospace Center	DE	
CERTH	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	GR	CERTH CENTRE FOR RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY HELLAS
AALTO	Aalto University	FI	A! Aalto University
ENEA	Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development	IT	
FENR	FEN Research GmbH	AT	
GRILLO	Grillo Werke AG	DE	

Summary

The Hybrid Sulphur cycle can significantly reduce the electrical energy demand for the electrolysis of water to hydrogen and oxygen. In a cyclic process, Sulphuric acid is first split into SO₂ and water in a reactor. The product of this process is fed to an electrolyzer together with additional water, producing Sulphuric acid and hydrogen. The Sulphuric acid can then be fed back into the reactor. The splitting reaction requires significant heat and, due to thermodynamic and kinetic reasons, only proceeds at temperatures around 850 °C. To provide this high-temperature heat, a demonstration plant of the Hybrid Sulphur cycle is to be coupled with the solar tower system HEHTRES from DLR in Jülich as part of the HySelect project. The HEHTRES system works with ceramic particles as a heat transfer and heat storage medium. In a centrifugal receiver (CentRec), the particles are heated up to 900 °C using concentrated solar radiation. As part of the activities in WP4, the CentRec was partially commissioned in the HEHTRES plant. In principle, the receiver system has the potential to cover the high-temperature heat demand of the Hybrid Sulphur cycle. So far, a maximum steady state outlet temperature of 700 °C at a particle mass flow rate of 0.8 kg/s has been achieved. Commissioning has been paused until March 2025 due to the winter in Germany. During the tests conducted so far, temperature hotspots have been observed in the rotating particle film flowing over the rotating inner receiver wall (inliner), which are presumably due to an inhomogeneous particle distribution and the resulting thermal deformations. It is possible that the inliner may overheat beyond the permitted continuous operating temperature if the CentRec is operated at particle outlet temperatures that exceed those achieved to date. The results achieved so far during the commissioning of the HEHTRES receiver therefore do not yet allow proof of a permanent supply of particles with a temperature of at least 900 °C in accordance with the requirements of the Sulphuric acid splitting reaction. For this reason, alternative solutions for heating a sufficient particle mass flow to the desired temperature level were sought as part of WP4. A promising concept for backup heating was identified from previous projects and a prototype of an electric particle heater was manufactured and tested. Essentially, this is a flat tube through which the particles flow, heated from the outside with heating conductors. During commissioning of the prototype, a particle mass flow of 15.6 kg/h was heated from ambient temperature to up to 920 °C. Based on these results, a heater concept for use in the HySelect demo plant was developed on the basis of the prototype design. The concept provides for the particle mass flow to be heated in several channels connected in parallel, similar to a plate heat exchanger. A rough design of the heater was created for this purpose, which is to be engineered, manufactured, assembled and commissioned as part of WP4 in 2025. At the same time, the commissioning activities for the HEHTRES system are being driven forward in order to check the performance of the receiver and demonstrate that it can consistently deliver a reproducible particle outlet temperature of ≥ 900 °C.

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1. Introduction

Thermochemical hydrogen production using the Hybrid Sulphur cycle is an interesting alternative to the conventional electrochemical production process. In addition to water, SO₂ is also fed into an electrolyzer. The amount of electrical energy required for electrolysis is significantly lower than in the classic process. The product of electrolysis is Sulphuric acid, which is split back into SO₂ and O₂ in an endothermic decomposition reaction in the splitting reactor. The splitting reaction only proceeds at an adequate degree at temperatures in the order of 650 °C – 950 °C [1].

Fig. 1: Schematic of the Hybrid Sulphur cycle principle [1].

In order to cover this significant heat demand, the Hybrid Sulphur cycle is to be coupled with a system for solar thermal heat generation (Concentrated Solar Technologies - CST). Such a system is being developed by the DLR Institute of Solar Research. A demonstration plant is currently being put into operation at DLR's solar tower in Jülich (HEHTRES plant). Ceramic particles are used as a heat transfer and storage medium. In the HySelect project, the planned demonstration plant for thermochemical hydrogen production via the Hybrid Sulphur cycle is to be coupled with the solar thermal plant in Jülich. This document summarizes the design of the HEHTRES system, the main results of commissioning and the integration concept of the HEHTRES facility into the HySelect pilot plant. It also discusses the development of an electrical heating device for the particles, as this heater is to be used as an auxiliary device to provide independently of solar availability and other fluctuations, a particle mass flow at a constant temperature level for the HySelect project.

2. Solar thermal heat generation

The Institute for Solar Research of DLR develops particle technology for point focusing solar tower systems since 2010. The particles used are a bauxite ceramic material consisting of a mixture of different aluminum ores. Originally developed as an auxiliary material used in the fracking industry, those granular proppants also have advantageous properties as a bulk material for the use in solar thermal power plants. Some of the key technical data of the particles used in the HEHTRES facility are listed in Table 1. In order to heat the particles by the concentrated solar irradiation, a receiver system is required, that engages the grains in contact with the solar irradiation. Therefore, DLR developed a centrifugal receiver system (CentRec®), in which the particles and the concentrated solar irradiation are in direct contact, providing an efficient heat transfer to the particles. Additionally, a unique advantage of this receiver is the capability to adjust the particle residence time in the receiver, providing the possibility to control the outlet temperature of the particles (see chapter 2.1). This receiver

system was first demonstrated in 2017 at DLR solar tower in Jülich with a 500 kW centrifugal receiver. A maximum particle outlet temperature of 965 °C could be achieved [2]. The receiver technology was continuously developed and improved in the following years to enhance the durability and the controllability of the system. Since 2020, a precommercial scale particle loop system (see chapter 2.2) has been built up in the solar towers Jülich as part of the HEHTRES project with a 1 MW centrifugal receiver.

Table 1: Physical properties of bauxite particles used in the HEHTRES facility.

Property	Value	Remark	Source
Specific heat capacity	1200 J/kg*K	Bulk, average in operation range 400 – 900 °C	Measured by DLR
Thermal conductivity	2.63 W/m*K	Single particle, average in operation range 400 - 900 °C	2013 VDI Heat Atlas (D6.4 Tab. 1) [3]
Solar absorptance	0.9	-	Measured by DLR
Mean particle diameter	0.95 mm	-	Datasheet Carbo HSP [4]
Bulk density	2100 kg/m ³	-	Datasheet Carbo HSP [4]

2.1. CentRec working principle

Fig. 2 : Schematic of a solar tower system with CentRec (left) and result of DEM simulated centrifugal receiver operation (right).

A schematic of the solar tower system with CentRec receiver is shown in Fig. 2. The centrifugal receiver is essentially a cylindrical rotary drum. The drum is inclined 45 ° to the horizontal. At the upper end of the drum a cone-like structure guides and accelerates the feedstock evenly towards the beginning of the inliner. On the inner surface of the receiver, the particles form a closed film and move towards the lower opening of the inliner. Solar irradiation is reflected by means of a heliostat field which concentrates the radiation on the top of a tower, where the CentRec-receiver is located. The concentrated solar irradiation heats the particles in the receiver as they move as an opaque particle film from the inlet to outlet of the rotating inliner. The conveying speed of the particle film alongside the axis of the rotating cavity depends on

the rotational speed of the receiver. Thus, by controlling the axial particle speed and vice-versa the residence time as well as the particle mass flow the outlet temperature can be controlled.

2.2. Plant Layout HEHTRES facility

Fig. 3 : HEHTRES receiver installed in the solar towers at Jülich (DLR). Inner diameter: 1,6 m; Length: 3 m.

The HEHTRES facility is the first precommercial scale demo plant for CST with a particle loop using a centrifugal receiver. The receiver is designed for a particle mass flow from 1.1 to 1.6 kg*s⁻¹ corresponding to a power output in the range of 0.75 – 1 MW considering a particle outlet temperature of max. 900 °C. As the CentRec receiver is an integral component of the HEHTRES particle handling system, the terms 'CentRec receiver' and 'HEHTRES receiver' are used interchangeably within this document. A picture of the CentRec in maintenance position is shown in Fig. 3. The whole receiver structure is assembled on two parallel rails, allowing to move the unit between the receiver aperture on the edge of the tower, for solar operation, and back inside the tower for maintaining purposes. The receiver-drum is mounted on rollers within a holding frame. An electro motor is connected to the receiver via a chain, that transfers the rotational movement onto the receiver. Two co-rotating control cabinets process the measurement signals from the rotating part of the system and transmit them to the PLC of the main control cabinet via WiFi. The heated particles “fall off the inliner” at the end of the receiver and are collected via the stationary collecting ring and directed to an exhaust pipe.

The particles are fed via the outlet tube to a downpipe and enter the hot storage tank, where the grains remain until the heat is required. With a volume of 4.1 m³, it can store the total mass of particles in the system of 8000 kg and is designed for a maximum heat loss of 1.6 kW/m². To compensate those heat losses, trace heating elements are attached between the metallic shell of the silo and its thermal insulation (as shown in Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 : Hot storage with installed trace heating (left) and insulation (right).

Subsequently, a plate heat exchanger is situated downstream of the hot storage tank (see Fig. 5), in which the thermal energy stored in the particles is transferred to a glycol-water mixture, acting as a cooling medium. The cooled particles are then stored in a low temperature storage tank, designed for a maximum particle temperature of 400 °C and a max. heat loss of 1 kW/m². The particles exiting the cold storage, pass a double vibrating screen to separate coarse and fine material and are then conveyed back to the top of the solar tower using a bucket elevator. The particles exit the bucket elevator at the top of the solar tower and are conveyed horizontally with a vibrating chute to a buffer tank. From the buffer tank, the particle mass flow is fed to the receiver via a dosing conveyor chute (see Fig. 6), capable to adjust particle mass flow rates with an uncertainty < 1 %.

Fig. 5 : Plate heat exchanger without insulation currently installed in the HEHTRES facility in order to cool the particles coming from the hot storage.

Fig. 6 : Particle transportation and dosing system above the CentRec receiver, located in the top of the multi-focus solar tower Jülich.

The particle flow from the receiver, at the top of the solar tower, downwards to the grain feed of the bucket elevator, is driven by gravitational forces. Both storage tanks are designed to be capable of storing the entire particle mass within the system of 8000 kg. The receiver, the hot storage, as well as the plate heat exchanger are designed for a particle temperature of max.

900 °C. All other components in the particle cycle are designed for a max. temperature of 400 °C. A system diagram of the overall plant is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 : Schematic of the overall HEHTRES facility.

2.3. Commissioning of HEHTRES facility – preliminary results

As mentioned, the CentRec receiver as part of the HEHTRES facility is designed to heat a particle mass flow in the range from 1.1 to 1.6 kg/s up to a temperature of 900 °C. In order to detect possible defects in the system at an early stage, during the hot commissioning process, the particle outlet temperature of the receiver was increased gradually over several test days. Between each test day, the system, in particular the receiver, was inspected in detail and all anomalies were documented. During the hot commissioning phase in 2024 a maximum steady

state particle outlet temperature of 700 °C was reached. The solar conditions in northern Germany in autumn and arising winter time, yet did not allow to test the system for a longer period or even for the envisioned higher temperature level up to 900 °C particle outlet temperature. It has yet to be demonstrated whether the receiver is capable of delivering the desired outlet temperature. This will be investigated at the beginning of 2025, once solar conditions in Germany have improved once more following the onset of spring in 2025. In light of these considerations, this chapter is dedicated to an examination of the most recent results achieved at the highest attained outlet temperature of 700 °C (see Fig. 10). The tests were performed for a constant particle mass flow of 0.8 kg/s (see Fig. 8). In order to minimize mechanical stresses due to thermal expansion, particularly in the inliner, the radiation flux density to the aperture of the receiver was gradually increased within the safety margins considering the thermo-mechanical properties of the materials. (see Fig. 9).

Fig. 8 : Particle mass flow over time of the HEHTRES CentRec at the latest test day.

Fig. 9 : Flux density over time on the aperture of the HEHTRES CentRec at the latest test day.

Fig. 10 : Particle outlet temperature over time of the HEHTRES CentRec at the latest test day.

The signals that can be used for balancing the receiver are RT_PMA_01 - RT_PMA_03, representing the particle outlet temperature. This temperature initially rises almost sigmoidally close to 400 °C and then starts to fall steeply. This behavior is due to a safety function that is intended to protect against excessive mechanical stresses, caused by too fast thermal expansion in the inliner and leads to a defocus of the heliostats. From 10.45 a.m., the particle outlet temperature rises again up to 700 °C and can be maintained for 20 minutes. After that, the temperature can no longer be maintained due to the passage of clouds, reducing the direct normal irradiation (DNI) on this test day. The measured inliner temperatures are correspondingly aligned with the course of the outlet temperatures (see Fig. 11).

Fig. 11 : Inliner temperatures over time of the CentRec receiver during the test day, reaching 700 °C particle outlet temperature. Each signal represents one thermocouple measuring on the backside of the inliner.

The inliner temperatures measured rose on this test day to a maximum of 800 °C. As those are local temperature measurements, the inliner may have reached higher temperatures during operation. This should be emphasized since the inliner must not exceed a maximum continuous operating temperature of 1100 °C, according to the manufacturer [5]. Therefore, additional IR videos of the particle surface were recorded during operation to monitor the inliner surface temperature. Fig. 12 shows a snapshot of the receiver aperture during operation.

Fig. 12 : Snapshot of an IR video recorded of the HEHTRES receiver aperture during operation with a particle outlet temperature of 700 °C.

With the help of the IR camera, temperatures of over 780 °C can be measured in the receiver. A partially uneven temperature stratification of the particle film temperature was observed. The cause of those hotspots is not fully understood, yet. It is possible that these are areas in the particle film that hardly experience any movement or mixing. Therefore, excessive heating of the particles takes place in this area due to an increased dwell time. During the cold commissioning of the HEHTRES receiver, it was observed that the particle film showed some areas during operation where the inliner is not fully covered with particles. As this has already been observed in previous projects [6], this is the most likely cause of the inhomogeneous temperature distribution in the particle film. The inliner is made of a nickel-based alloy (Inconel 617). Therefore, the emission coefficient for this measurement was assumed to be $\epsilon = 0.85$, corresponding to the data from the literature for Inconel at temperatures around 1000 °C [7]. When inspecting the receiver after the hot commissioning process for particle outlet temperature of 550 °C, the occurrence of tempering colors of the metallic inliner was observed, which indicates increased local heating (see Fig. 13). It is regarded as conceivable that the temperature difference between the particles at the outlet and the inliner could rise even further during operation if higher outlet temperatures than the already reached 700 °C would be applied. It is thus conceivable that the receiver will be unable to maintain a constant operating state at the targeted particle outlet temperature of 900 °C.

Fig. 13 : Inliner of the HEHTRES receiver after operation with 550 °C particle outlet temperature.

3. Electrical particle heater development as a back-up solution

As mentioned in chapter 2.3, yet it is not clear whether the HEHTRES receiver fulfills the requirement of a particle outlet temperature of at least 900 °C in accordance with the Grand Agreement. This was a foreseen risk in the DoW and as part of the work in WP4, alternative options were sought for feeding particles to the splitting reactor of the planned HySelect demo plant at the targeted temperature level with the desired mass flow. An electric particle heater had already been used as part of the EU-funded predecessor project PEGASUS [8]. Under laboratory conditions, particles were heated from ambient temperature to over 900 °C and fed to a prototype of the splitting reactor, which is now to be used as a further development in the HySelect project. Although the particles were successfully heated to the targeted temperature level, there were some difficulties when operating the heater. There were frequent defects in the heater, which significantly impaired the heating performance (see chapter 3.1). It was therefore decided to first build an additional prototype to investigate the performance of the heater in more detail and to evaluate if the second prototype (see chapter 4) would be applicable as role model for an electric heater concept that could be used in a scaled version in the HySelect demo system.

3.1. Design of the heater prototype and test rig setup

The prototype heater consists of a heated flat tube (see Fig. 14). Particles flow through the tube in the form of a moving bed. The outside of the tube is wrapped with heating conductors, which transfer their heat to the particles via the tube wall. The particle movement is driven by gravitational forces, as the tube is inclined at 45° to the earth's gravitational field. This inclination was chosen due to special limitations of the available height for the test rig. The shape of the tube provides a very favorable ratio of surface area to volume for heat transfer, with the tube surface acting as a heat transfer surface. A total of 4 electro resistive heating conductors are positioned sequentially along the 1 m long pipe. 8 thermocouples are attached at each trace heating element, constantly observing the temperature of each conductor at various points preventing the trace heaters to overheat. Given the importance of accurate

temperature measurement and control, supported by the experience gained from the PEGASUS project, a redundant thermocouple arrangement has been implemented to enhance system reliability. The design of the heater used in the PEGASUS project was similar to the prototype presented here. However, only one thermocouple was used to control each trace heating element. Since this heater design does not guarantee a uniform heat distribution from the heating conductors into the metallic tube, potential local overheating of the heating bands could occur. As a result of the old design, individual heating conductors repeatedly failed and had to be replaced.

According to the manufacturer, the trace heating elements must not exceed a maximum operating temperature of 1000 °C. Since the intended particle outlet temperature is 900 °C and above, it is considered as necessary to provide a high resolution of thermal surveillance, using a high number of thermo couples for each heating element, while operating the elements close to its max. operation conditions, but still be able to provide a controllable system, preventing the unit from damaging.

Fig. 14: CAD model of the heater flat tube with heating bands wrapped around.

The heater is insulated from the surroundings by microporous insulation. The insulation is held in place by a metallic envelope. As part of the commissioning and performance tests for this prototype, the heater is integrated into a heat transfer test stand. Above the heater there is a feeding hopper in which cold particles are stored. The cold particles are fed from the container into the heater and heated to the desired outlet temperature. The heated particles accumulate in front of a perforated orifice. The orifice diameter can be used to adjust the particle mass flow. Once the particles have passed through the orifice plate, they fall into a separate heat

exchanger test assembly. In the cross-sectional area of the heat exchanger through which the flow passes, there is a regular packed column over which the particles trickle. This increases their residence time, the total available particle mass and thus enhances the volumetric heat transfer. Ambient air enters the heat exchanger from the bottom and flows counterflow to the trickling particles towards the top. Particles and air are in direct contact for heat exchange. The cooled particles are collected at the bottom in a collection container downstream of the heat exchanger.

Fig. 15: Electrical particle heater test stand.

3.2. Results of commissioning of the heater prototype

In analogy to the CentRec testing in the HEHTRES system, also for the tested particle heater the particle outlet temperature was increased stepwise during the hot commissioning period over several test. After reaching a new temperature level, the heater was inspected for anomalies and damage. This served to detect and rectify defects at an early stage before irreparable damage to the heater could occur. During the commissioning, steady state outlet temperatures of up to 920 °C were achieved at a particle mass flow rate of 15.6 kg/h. Fig. 16 shows the measurement data of the outlet temperatures of the corresponding test. At the outlet of the heater, 3 thermocouples constantly measure the temperature of the moving particle bed. To preheat the system and not “waste” the limited amount of particle in the available in the particle feeding hopper, until 10.10 a.m. no particle flow was in the system. This means that the particles around the thermocouples at the outlet are only heated via heat conduction through the bed.

Fig. 16: Particle outlet temperature over time of the heater prototype for the latest test.

The outlet temperatures rise slowly up to 250 °C. The mass flow is then started and the outlet temperatures rise to around 950 °C in a few minutes and to a constant temperature of 920 °C within the following 135 min. The repeated peaks in the outlet temperatures are due to blockages that briefly interrupt the particle flow and were caused by a faulty component of the test stand. For future heaters, this behavior is therefore no longer expected. The measurement results from the commissioning of the heater prototype show, that this design is entirely suitable for reproducibly raising the particles to the temperature level required by the splitting reactor of the HySelect demo plant. It was therefore decided to choose a design based on the tested prototype for the heater to be used in this demonstration plant.

4. Integration of the solar tower system with particle loop in the hydrogen production process

As discussed in chapter 3 an electrical particle heater will be installed in the HySelect demo plant in order to stabilize the temperature of the particle feed into the SO₂ splitting reactor if required. The heater can also serve as an interface between the HEHTRES and HySelect system. Based on the activities in WP6, the splitting reactor requires 302.4 kg/h of particles at a temperature of ≥ 900 °C. This corresponds to 19 times the power that the before described prototype particle heater can supply. A scale-up is therefore necessary to cover the power requirement for the application in the HySelect demo plant. The heat flow, \dot{Q}_P , transferred to the particles by the heater prototype can be calculated for the steady state case from the experimental results of the commissioning phase according to Eq. 1.

$$\dot{Q}_P = \dot{m}_P * c_{p,P} * (T_{out} - T_{in}) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

With particle mass flow of $\dot{m}_P = 15.6 \text{ kg/h}$, an outlet temperature of $T_{out} = 1193.15 \text{ K}$, a particle inlet temperature of $T_{in} = 293.15 \text{ K}$ and an averaged particle heat capacity of $c_{p,P} = 1056.65 \text{ J/(kg} \cdot \text{K)}$, the transferred heat flow can be determined to $\dot{Q}_P = 4.12 \text{ kW}$. This balance together with the dimensions of the prototype heater were used as the basis for

determining the dimensions of the heater for the HySelect plant. This heater should be able to heat a particle mass flow of around 398 kg/h from ambient temperature to over 900 °C permanently and reproducibly. This corresponds to an aimed transferred heat flow of 100 kW. This dimensioning serves as a safety margin. Based on the flat tube design of the prototype, the heater for the HySelect plant is scaled similarly like plate heat exchanger. Fig. 17 shows a sketch of the envisioned particle heater. The heater is constituted by sheet metal plates of high-temperature steel (e.g. 1.4841) with heating conductors subsequently attached at one side transferring their heat to the particles via the plates. The plates are arranged to form a total of 16 channels through which the incoming particle mass flow is guided. In order to achieve an even particle distribution for all 16 channels, a feed container is installed upstream of the actual heater, in which the particles accumulate as a particle bed, distributed evenly over the cross-sectional area of the heater. Based on the flat tube design of the prototype (see chapter 3), 4 heating conductors are used per channel over the height. Transferring the same methodology to the here presented approach, a total of around 64 heating conductors are needed. Thermocouples measure the local heating band temperatures in order to regulate the heating power individually and to prevent local overheating and thereby increasing the reliability of the particle heater. Only one thermocouple is used for each of the two top heating conductors, as the temperature difference and hence the heat absorbance of the moving bed is large enough so that no excess temperatures are to be expected in the upper heater area. Three thermocouples each are used for the lower two heating conductors for a more precise temperature monitoring of the trace heating elements, operating more closely to its maximum operating temperature. A flange is available below the heating unit, providing the capability for direct coupling to the splitting reactor.

Fig. 17: Basic design of the electrical particle heater to be used for the HySelect plant.

As already mentioned in Deliverable 2.1, the heater is to be installed downstream of the hot storage tank of the HEHTRES facility. The heated particles are fed directly into the splitting reactor. It is important to stress, that this heater will serve as a backup solution and not replace the CentRec of the HEHTRES system. For periods of poor solar availability or high fluctuation, the particle heater will serve as a backup solution and can guarantee the provision of a particle

mass flow at the required temperature level, allowing to operate the splitting reactor constantly and at stable conditions. Besides, if the required particle temperature of ≥ 900 °C would not be achieved using the current version of the receiver (see chapter 2.3), the particles would already be preheated to the highest possible temperature by solar concentrated power during the receiver operation. The temperature difference of the particles leaving the receiver and the required target temperature would then be overcome in the particle heater.

5. Conclusions

As part of the activities in WP4, the CentRec receiver was partially commissioned in the HEHTRES plant. The particle technology for solar tower systems with the CentRec as a receiver system has the potential to cover industrial high-temperature heat demand such as needed in a Hybrid Sulphur cycle, for which a demonstration plant will be realized as part of WP8 of the HySelect project. Based on the results achieved so far of the partial commissioning of the HEHTRES receiver, it has not yet been possible to prove whether the system fulfills the requirement of a permanent supply of hot particles with a temperature of at least 900 °C. The maximum steady state particle outlet temperature of the receiver achieved to date is 700 °C at a mass flow rate of 0.8 kg/s. Commissioning has been paused until March 2025 due to the winter in Germany. During the tests conducted so far, thermal hotspots were observed on the inliner and the opaque particle film, which are presumably due to an inhomogeneous particle distribution and movement upon the rotating inliner (see chapter 2.3). There is a risk that the inliner could overheat beyond the permissible continuous operating temperature if the CentRec is operated at conditions to achieve higher particle outlet temperatures than those previously achieved. For this reason, alternative solutions for heating the design particle mass flow to the desired temperature level were sought as part of WP4. A small-scale prototype of an electro resistive heater was manufactured and tested successfully, providing a particle mass flow of 15.6 kg/h with constant temperatures of 920 °C (see section 3.1). This forms the basis for the scale up of a particle heater, to be used in the HySelect testing procedure. Corresponding to the results described in section 3.1, a concept for a 100 kW heater was developed for use in the HySelect demo system based on the design of the prototype. The particle mass flow is to be heated in an arrangement similarly to a shell and plate heat exchanger. The designed heater is capable of heating a particle mass flow of 398 kg/h from ambient temperature to ≥ 900 °C. The basic engineering of the heater was performed for this purpose, which is to be detail engineered, manufactured, assembled and commissioned as part of WP4 in 2025. At the same time, the hot commissioning activities for the CentRec-Receiver and the HEHTRES facility are being driven forward in order to check the performance of the receiver and to verify that it can permanently deliver a reproducible particle outlet temperature of ≥ 900 °C.

6. References

- [1] Orhan, M. F., Dincer, I., Rosen, M. A., Kanoglu, M. (2012). Integrated hydrogen production options based on renewable and nuclear energy sources. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **16/8**, 6059–6082.
- [2] Ebert, M., Amsbeck, L., Jensch, A., Hertel, J., Rheinländer, J., Trebing, D., Uhlig, R., Buck, R. Upscaling, Manufacturing and Test of a Centrifugal Particle Receiver. In: *International Sustainable Energy Conference 2018*.
- [3] Verein Deutscher Ingenieure (2010). *VDI Heat Atlas*, 2. Aufl. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- [4] Datasheet. CarboCeramics CARBOHSP.
<https://www.carboceramics.com/products/oilfield-solutions/well-completion/carbohsp>
(letzter Zugriff am 27.11.2024).

- [5] Datasheet. Nicrofer® 5520 Co – alloy 617. https://www.vdm-metals.com/fileadmin/user_upload/Downloads/Data_Sheets/Datenblatt_VDM_Alloy_617.pdf (letzter Zugriff am 6.12.2024).
- [6] D. Thomey, M. Wullenkord, V.K. Thanda, H. Barbri, M. Lubkoll, J. Rheinländer (2021). D6.4 – Report on solar simulator campaign results, economic prospects of technology and capability for further scale-up. Framework Programme of the European Union.
- [7] Balat-Pichelin, M., Sans, J.-L., Bêche, E., Charpentier, L., Ferrière, A., Chomette, S. (2021). Emissivity at high temperature of Ni-based superalloys for the design of solar receivers for future tower power plants. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* **227**, 111066.
- [8] D. Thomey, C. Agrafiotis, V.K. Thanda, J. Rheinländer (2021). D6.2 – Pilot-scale modules including all necessary peripherals installed at solar facility and coupled, ready for combined operation. Framework Programme of the European Union.